

APPENDIX G

Usability

Table G.1

Usability checklist

	Item	Yes/No	Comments
1	It is easy to learn how to use the application.		
2	It is easy to use the application.		
3	Steps to use the application are easy to follow.		
4	Labels and texts on buttons are clear and concise.		
5	Conserve overall consistency and behavior with the mobile platform.		
6	Minimalist design - Excessive features are removed.		
7	Content is concise and clear.		
8	Provide feedback to the user about the state of the system.		
9	Number of buttons/links are reasonable.		
10	Elements of the interface provide visual feedback when are pressed.		
11	Ensures that not any message/feedback is being covered by the user's hand or finger.		
12	Colors used provide a good contrast.		
13	Colors used provide good readability.		
14	Icons are clear to understand - there is no ambiguity.		
15	Font size and spacing ensure good readability.		
16	Speak the language of the users (not technical)		
17	It helps users recognize, diagnose and recover errors.		
18	Error messages are free of technical language		
19	Error messages clearly explain how to solve the problem.		
20	Help messages are clear and unambiguous.		
21	Instructions are easily visible or easily recoverable when appropriate.		
22	By making mistakes, mistakes can be easily corrected.		
24	Images (stars and/or atoms) allow to identify their number and associated color.		
25	The tutorial is clear and allows you to understand the dynamics of the game.		